

Statistical Assessment and Hydrological Utility of Multiple Gridded Precipitation Datasets in Upper Aras Basin

Hamed HAFIZI^{1,2}, Ali Arda ŞORMAN¹

¹Eskisehir Technical University, Faculty of Graduate School of Sciences, Department of Civil Engineering

²Kabul Polytechnic University, Faculty of Water Resources and Environmental Engineering, Department of Hydraulics and Hydraulic Structures

hamedhafizi@eskisehir.edu.tr; hamedhafizi@kpu.edu.af; asorman@eskisehir.edu.tr

ABSTRACT

Precipitation is an essential meteorological forcing for hydrologic modeling, and its accurate estimation requires installation and maintenance of dense gauge networks, which is limited for many regions. Conversely, Gridded Precipitation Datasets (GPDs) can be an alternative to carry out research over complex topography and snow dominant regions. Therefore, this study aims to evaluate the spatio-temporal consistency and hydrologic utility of four GPDs (ERA5, CHIRPv2.0, IMERGHHFv0.6, and PERSIANN) over a mountainous basin (Upper Aras basin) in the eastern part of Turkey. The Kling–Gupta Efficiency (KGE) is used to compare GPDs with observed precipitation directly, and the Hanssen–Kuiper (HK) skill score is utilized to assess the detectability strength of selected GPDs for different precipitation intensities. Moreover, the hydrologic utility of GPDs is tested by exploiting a conceptual rainfall-runoff model under Kling–Gupta Efficiency (KGE) and Nash–Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) metrics. Generally, all GPDs show low performance compared with observed precipitation directly while their performance considerably increases for streamflow simulation. ERA5 show high reproducibility in streamflow (KGE = 0.86), followed by IMERGHHFv06 (KGE = 0.85), PERSIANN (KGE = 0.77), and CHIRPv2.0 (KGE = 0.70), for the entire period (2015–2019) of the study.

Keywords: Gridded Precipitation Datasets, Validation, Hydrologic Modeling, Mountainous Basin.

INTRODUCTION

Precipitation is one of the essential components of the hydrological cycle. Meanwhile, precipitation magnitude varies over short horizontal distances because of the orographic effects and altitude-precipitation relation (Bookhagen and Burbank, 2006; Herold et al., 2017). Traditionally, the amount of precipitation is estimated by gauge installation over the ground and provides a direct physical precipitation observation (Sevruk, 1987; Shi et al., 2017). However, the scarcity or non-existent gauge observation over complex topography and highly elevated regions has always been a great challenge for accurate precipitation estimation in recent decades (Hafizi and Sorman, 2021; Nazeer et al., 2022). On the other hand, Gridded Precipitation Datasets (GPDs) in combination with rainfall-runoff modeling can be an alternative to provide essential data for hydro-meteorological studies over gauge scarce regions (Nazeer et al., 2022).

In recent decades, various Gridded Precipitation Datasets (GPDs) varying in spatial and temporal resolution have been developed and they can generally be classified into the following groups; (1) GPDs which use only satellite information such as Precipitation Estimation from Remotely Sensed Information using Artificial Neural Networks (PERSIANN) (Sorooshian et al., 2000), (2) GPDs obtained from numerical weather prediction models output such as European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) reanalysis fifth-generation (ERA5) (Hersbach and Dee, 2016), (3) those that only use in-situ data information such as Climate Prediction Center unified (CPC) (Xie et al., 2007), and (4) GPDs that use multi-sources information such as Climate Hazards group InfraRed Precipitation version 2.0 (CHIRP V2.0) (Funk et al., 2015) and Integrated Multi-satellitE Retrievals for GPM (IMERG) final run V06 (Huffman et al., 2020).

Furthermore, several authors reported the performance of GPDs either by direct comparison with in-situ precipitation data (Amjad et al., 2020; Beck et al., 2019; Lu et al., 2021; Qi et al., 2021; Satgé et al., 2020; Uysal et al., 2021) or using GPDs as a meteorological forcing in the hydrologic models and

comparing the simulated streamflow with observed streamflow (Dembélé et al., 2020; Hafizi and Sorman, 2021; Su et al., 2021; Uysal and Şorman, 2021).

This study aims to evaluate four GPDs such as ERA5, CHIRPv2.0, IMERGHHFv0.6, and PERSIANN by direct comparison with observed precipitation, considering the seasonal variability of precipitation in daily time step and hydrologic utility under two different scenarios for five water years from October 2014 to September 2019.

The paper is summarized as follows: Section 1 presents a comprehensive introduction to GPDs. Section 2 gives information on materials and methods. Section 3 presents the results and detailed discussions, and finally, conclusions are conveyed in Section 4.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

The current analysis is carried out over the upper Aras River basin (39:50:16N-41:50:19E), situated at the headwater of Aras River in the northeast of Turkey (Figure 1). The drainage area is around 2730 km², and its outlet is controlled by the D24A096 stream gauging station. Moreover, the basin is mountainous where its elevation varies from 1646m to 3156m, and precipitation occurs in the form of

Figure 1. Geographic location and elevation map of Upper Aras River basin and hydro-meteorological station distribution over the study area.

rain and snow. In the same way, the basin surface is covered by agricultural area (15%), bare land (30.8%), and grassland/pasture (50.4%) (Sorman et al., 2020). The topographic complexity, high altitude, and snow dominant characteristics of the basin are advantageous in validating GPDs and operating hydrologic models for areas under such difficult conditions.

Data

The daily precipitation and temperature data from 12 meteorological stations are provided by the General Directorate of Meteorology (GDM). The daily observed streamflow for the D24A096 stream gauging station at the basin outlet is obtained from the General Directorate of Hydraulic Works (GDHW). The data were made available from 2015 to 2019 hydrologic years. Moreover, four Gridded Precipitation Datasets (GPDs) such as European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) reanalysis fifth-generation (ERA5), Climate Hazards group InfraRed Precipitation version 2.0 (CHIRP V2.0), Integrated Multi-satellitE Retrievals for GPM (IMERG) final run V06, and Precipitation Estimation from Remotely Sensed Information using Artificial Neural Networks (PERSIANN) are gathered from various sources which are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. List of selected GPDs in the study, Abbreviations in the data source column; G, gauge; S, satellite; R; Reanalysis.

Name	Data source(s)	Spatial resolution	Spatial coverage	Temporal resolution	Reference
ERA5	R	0.25°	50° N/S	Hourly	(Hersbach and Dee, 2016)
CHIRP V2.0	R, S	0.05°	50° N/S	Daily	(Funk et al., 2015)
IMERGHFv06	S, G	0.10°	60° N/S	30 min	(Huffman et al., 2020)
PERSIANN	S	0.25°	60° N/S	Hourly	(Hsu et al., 1999)

Statistical metrics

Three statistical indicators (Table 2) are applied to evaluate the consistency of selected GPDs over time and space and their performance for streamflow prediction. The Kling–Gupta Efficiency (KGE) (Gupta et al., 2009; Kling et al., 2012) and its Pearson Correlation coefficient (r), Bias (β), and Variability ratio

Table 2. Statistical metrics used in study (optimal value is unity for each of them)

Performance metrics	Equations	Description
Kling Gupta Efficiency and its components	$KGE=1-[(r-1)^2+(\beta-1)^2+(\gamma-1)^2]^{0.5}$ $r=\frac{1}{n}\sum_{i=1}^n(o_i-\mu_o)(s_i-\mu_s)/(\delta_o\times\delta_s),$ $\beta=\frac{\mu_s}{\mu_o}, \quad \gamma=(\delta_s\times\mu_o)/(\mu_s\times\delta_o)$	<i>R</i> (Pearson correlation coefficient), <i>β</i> (Bias) is the ratio of estimated and observed mean, <i>γ</i> (Variability Ratio) is the ratio of estimated and observed coefficients of variation, <i>μ</i> and <i>δ</i> are the distribution mean and standard deviation where <i>s</i> and <i>o</i> indicate estimated and observed. <i>M</i> (Miss); when the observed precipitation is not detected. <i>F</i> (False); when the precipitation is detected but not observed, <i>H</i> (Hit); when the observed precipitation is correctly detected, <i>CN</i> (Correct Negative); a no precipitation event is detected. <i>n</i> is the sample size of the
Hanssen-Kuiper	$HK=\frac{(H\times CN)-(F\times M)}{(H+M)(F+CN)}$	

Nash–Sutcliffe Efficiency	$NSE=1-\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (Q_i^{sim}-Q_i^{ob})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (Q_i^{ob}-\overline{Q_i^{ob}})^2}$	observed or calculated streamflow. Q_i^{ob} and Q_i^{sim} present the observed and simulated streamflow, $\overline{Q_i^{ob}}$ present the mean observed streamflow.
----------------------------------	---	--

(γ) is used for the direct comparison of GPDs with observed precipitation. Furthermore, the Hanssen-Kuiper (HK) skill score is used to measure the detectability strength of GPDs by considering five precipitation intensity thresholds such as no-precipitation (less than 1 mm/day), light precipitation (1-5 mm/day), moderate precipitation (5-20 mm/day), heavy precipitation (20-40 mm/day) and violent precipitation (more than 40 mm/day) (Zambrano-Bigiarini et al., 2017). Moreover, for the hydrologic utility of GPDs, Nash–Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) and KGE metrics are utilized. For the streamflow reproducibility, two scenarios are considered; when the model parameters are calibrated by observed precipitation and then the observed precipitation is replaced by each GPD (Scheme-1), where for Scheme-2, the model parameters are calibrated by each GPD separately. The conceptual TUW model is used for the precipitation-runoff modeling, and its structure is similar to the HBV model. The TUW model has 15 parameters and is able to simulate runoff, snow, and soil moisture by using daily precipitation, temperature, and evaporation data (Parajka et al., 2007). The model parameters are calibrated by hydroPSO R package which includes particle swarm global optimization algorithm (Zambrano-Bigiarini, 2020). The model parameters are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Model parameter range and optimum values for observed precipitation and GPDs. Number of the column indicates: 0, parameter range; 1, Obs; 2, ERA5; 3, CHIRPv2.0; 4, IMERGHFv06; and 5, PERSIANN.

Parameter and Units	0	1	2	3	4	5
Snow correction factor—SCF (-)	0.9–1.5	1.5	1.12	1.03	1.1	1.4
Degree-day factor—DDF (mm/°C/day)	0.0–5.0	3.6	0.3	0.51	2.2	1.8
Temperature threshold above which precipitation is rain—Tr (°C)	1.0–3.0	2.3	1.74	1.43	1.8	3.0
Temperature threshold below which precipitation is snow—Ts (°C)	-3.0–1.0	1.0	-0.01	-0.1	-0.9	0.9
Temperature threshold above which melt starts—Tm (°C)	-2.0–2.0	1.7	-1.86	0.87	1.0	1.5
Parameter related to the limit for potential evaporation—Lpart (-)	0.0–1.0	1.0	0.6	0.36	0.5	0.9
Field capacity—FC (mm)	0.0–600	43.4	317.8	45.3	71.1	94.7
Nonlinear parameter for runoff production—Beta (-)	0.0–20	6.0	1.82	5.52	3.1	0.1
Constant percolation rate—K ₀ (mm/day)	0.0–2.0	0.8	1.09	0.73	1.0	1.1
Storage coefficient for very fast response—K ₁ (day)	2.0–30	20.6	23.1	20.0	15.7	15.1
Storage coefficient for fast response—K ₂ (day)	30–250	40.1	38.3	50.9	40.2	35.5
Storage coefficient for slow response—lsuz (day)	1.0–100	52.2	87.9	57.5	58.7	66.1
Threshold storage state—cperc (mm)	0.0–8.0	5.2	5.0	6.9	7.7	0.3
Maximum base at low flows—bmax (day)	0.0–30	3.1	13.6	7.7	9.0	19.6
Free scaling parameter—croute (day ² /mm)	0.0–50	35.2	27.3	24.3	11.1	39.5

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Mean daily precipitation

Figure 2 presents mean daily precipitation and its bias for the entire period (2015-2019) and four seasons retrieved from observed precipitation and all GPDs at the regional scale. Based on observed precipitation, the region experiences 1.36mm/day precipitation for the entire period, where this amount increases to 2.1mm/day for the spring (MAM) season. Furthermore, the region receives less precipitation (0.75mm/day) during the summer (JJA), which is pretty natural, and precipitation reaches 1.3mm/day

for the autumn (SON) season. Finally, spring precipitation is followed by winter (DJF) season precipitation (1.36mm/day).

Figure 2. Mean Daily precipitation and bias at the regional scale obtained from observed and four GPDs for the entire period and four seasons. Legend text color presents: reanalysis (green), satellite and reanalysis (sky blue), gauge and satellite (red), and satellite (blue).

Among all GPDs, the PERSIANN dataset consistently underestimates mean daily precipitation compared to observed precipitation, while CHIRPv2.0 only underestimates winter precipitation. The rest of the GPDs show more precipitation for the entire period and four seasons; for example, ERA5 shows the highest overestimate (bias; 0.9mm/day) during the spring season, followed by IMERGHHFv06 (bias; 0.82mm/day) during the winter season. Overall, the range of under/overestimation of GPDs for mean daily precipitation is between -0.75mm to 0.9mm.

GPD reliability in space and time

Figure 3 presents the reliability of each GPD at the regional scale in the form of KGE and its components for the entire period and four seasons. For the entire period (2015-2019), ERA5 presents high performance (KGE; 0.28) followed by CHIRPv2.0 (KGE; 0.14), IMERGHHFv06 (KGE; 0.14), and

Figure 3. GPD reliability at the regional scale for the entire period and four seasons is expressed in the form of KGE and its components. Y-axis color presents: reanalysis (green), satellite and reanalysis (sky blue), gauge and satellite (red), and satellite (blue).

PERSIANN (KGE; 0.03) where ERA5 shows high correlation coefficient among other GPDs. Likewise, except PERSIANN, all GPDs overestimate bias and underestimate variability ratio, respectively. For the seasonal performance, all GPDs show lower performance during the summer season where only PERSIANN shows poor performance during the autumn season. IMERGHHFv06 presents high KGE (0.20) for the winter season, where the rest of the GPDs perform weakly.

The GPD performance at the station location is expressed by KGE and its components (Figure 4). ERA5, CHIRPv2.0, and IMERGHHFv06 are more effective in the southern region, where PERSIANN shows weak performance in general but presents better KGE in the northern parts compared to CHIRPv2.0 and IMERGHHFv06. Furthermore, IMERGHHFv06 shows higher KGE within the basin, followed by CHIRPSv2.0, ERA5, and PERSIANN. Moreover, all GPDs show a high correlation coefficient (r) where no clear trend is observed for bias (β), and only PERSIANN overestimates variability ratio (γ) spatially.

Figure 4. GPD reliability at the station location expressed in the form of KGE and its components considering the entire period (2015-2019) precipitation. Title color presents: reanalysis (green), satellite and reanalysis (sky blue), gauge and satellite (red), and satellite (blue).

Figure 5 shows the detectability strength of each GPD at the regional scale and is expressed in the form of Hanssen–Kuiper (HK) score for five distinct daily precipitation intensities, considering the entire period and seasonal variability of precipitation over the region. In general, it is observed that GPD detectability is more effective for precipitation intensity less than 1mm/day. Furthermore, GPDs show

high detectability for low intensity, and detectability strength decreases as the precipitation intensity increases. However, there can be some fluctuations in the pattern; for example, IMERGHHFv06 is able to detect moderate precipitation with 0.17 compared to light precipitation with 0.10 during the summer

Figure 5. GPD detection ability for various precipitation intensity expressed in the form of Hanssen-Kuiper (HK) score for the entire period and four seasons. Y-axis color presents: reanalysis (green), satellite and reanalysis (sky blue), gauge and satellite (red), and satellite (blue).

season. ERA5 shows the highest detectability for all precipitation intensities compared to CHIRPv2.0 and IMERGHHFv06, whereas PERSIANN consistently shows a weak performance in capturing precipitation events.

GPD strength for streamflow prediction

Figure 6 presents observed and simulated streamflow for two schemes, including observed precipitation and four GPDs for the Upper Aras basin. The daily simulated streamflow is reproduced by TUW model considering five water years (2015-2019) which is classified into two parts, model calibration (October 2014 -September 2016) and model validation (October 2016 -September 2019).

Figure 6. Observed and simulated streamflow from gauge precipitation data and four GPDs for the calibration (October 2014 -September 2016) and validation (October 2016 -September 2019) periods. Title color presents: reanalysis (green), satellite and reanalysis (sky blue), gauge and satellite (red), and satellite (blue).

Figure 7 displays the performance of GPDs for streamflow prediction in stream gauging station (D24A096) located at the outlet of the basin. The model shows high performance using gauge observations in both the calibration and validation periods. On the other hand, except CHIRPv2.0 dataset, all GPDs do not show the same success in Scheme-1, although having high correlation ratios and high bias. Furthermore, when GPDs are used as meteorological forcing for the model parameter calibration individually, all GPDs show high reproducibility of streamflow for the calibration period and show better performance for the validation period compared to gauge precipitation data. Among all GPDs, CHIRPSv2.0 indicates a different trend in that it shows an increasing calibration performance in Scheme-2 (KGE; 0.86) as compared to Scheme-1 (KGE; 0.68), but a decreasing result for the validation stage with a KGE; 0.66 in Scheme-1 to KGE; 0.58 in Scheme-2. Table 3 summarizes TUW model parameter ranges and calibration results for observed precipitation and GPDs.

Figure 7. Statistical metrics computed between observed and simulated streamflow forced by gauge precipitation and GPDs for the calibration, validation and entire period. Y-axis color presents: reanalysis (green), satellite and reanalysis (sky blue), gauge and satellite (red), and satellite (blue).

CONCLUSIONS

This study evaluated the stability of four GPDs (ERA5, CHIRPv2.0, IMERGHHFv06, and PERSIANN) by directly comparing GPDs with in-situ precipitation derived from 12 meteorological stations. Furthermore, the hydrologic utility of GPDs for streamflow prediction is assessed by two standard calibration/validation schemes considering five water years (2015-2019). Moreover, three statistical metrics (KGE, HK, and NSE) are considered for direct comparison and hydrologic utility of GPDs. The main conclusions are summarized as follows:

- All GPDs present low performance when compared directly with observed precipitation but show better correlation and high/low bias and variability ratio. The highest performance is obtained by ERA5 (KGE; 0.40) during the autumn season.
- GPDs show high detectability for low intensity precipitation and low detectability for high intensity precipitation events. Only IMERGHHFv06 show an unclear trend of intensity-detectability for light and moderate precipitation.
- All GPDs show relatively higher ability for streamflow prediction as compared to direct precipitation observations. In addition, GPDs present higher reproducibility when model parameters are calibrated by each GPD individually (Scheme-2). CHIRPv2.0 is the only GPD that shows high reproducibility when the model is calibrated by gauge precipitation data.

Future work will include more GPDs for direct precipitation comparison and hydrologic simulations over other basins of Turkey.

REFERENCES

- Amjad, M., Yilmaz, M. T., Yucel, I., & Yilmaz, K. K. (2020). *Performance evaluation of satellite-and model-based precipitation products over varying climate and complex topography*. Journal of Hydrology, 584, 124707.
- Beck, H. E., Pan, M., Roy, T., Weedon, G. P., Pappenberger, F., Van Dijk, A. I., . . . Wood, E. F. (2019). *Daily evaluation of 26 precipitation datasets using Stage-IV gauge-radar data for the CONUS*. Hydrology and Earth System Sciences, 23(1), 207-224.
- Bookhagen, B., & Burbank, D. W. (2006). *Topography, relief, and TRMM-derived rainfall variations along the Himalaya*. Geophysical Research Letters, 33(8).
- Dembélé, M., Ceperley, N., Zwart, S. J., Salvadore, E., Mariethoz, G., & Schaeffli, B. (2020). *Potential of satellite and reanalysis evaporation datasets for hydrological modelling under various model calibration strategies*. Advances in Water Resources, 143, 103667.
- Funk, C., Peterson, P., Landsfeld, M., Pedreros, D., Verdin, J., Shukla, S., . . . Hoell, A. (2015). *The climate hazards infrared precipitation with stations—a new environmental record for monitoring extremes*. Scientific data, 2(1), 1-21.
- Gupta, H. V., Kling, H., Yilmaz, K. K., & Martinez, G. F. (2009). *Decomposition of the mean squared error and NSE performance criteria: Implications for improving hydrological modelling*. Journal of Hydrology, 377(1-2), 80-91.
- Hafizi, H., & Sorman, A. A. (2021). *Assessment of Satellite and Reanalysis Precipitation Products for Rainfall–Runoff Modelling in a Mountainous Basin*. Environmental Sciences Proceedings, 8(1), 25.
- Herold, N., Behrangi, A., & Alexander, L. V. (2017). *Large uncertainties in observed daily precipitation extremes over land*. Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres, 122(2), 668-681.
- Hersbach, H., & Dee, D. (2016). *ERA5 reanalysis is in production*, ECMWF Newsletter, Vol. 147. Reading, United Kingdom: ECMWF www.ecmwf.int/sites/default/files/elibrary/2016/16299newsletterno147spring2016.pdf.
- Hsu, K. I., Gupta, H. V., Gao, X., & Sorooshian, S. (1999). *Estimation of physical variables from multichannel remotely sensed imagery using a neural network: Application to rainfall estimation*. Water Resources Research, 35(5), 1605-1618.
- Huffman, G. J., Bolvin, D. T., Braithwaite, D., Hsu, K.-L., Joyce, R. J., Kidd, C., . . . Tan, J. (2020). *Integrated Multi-satellite Retrievals for the Global Precipitation Measurement (GPM) Mission (IMERG)*. In Satellite Precipitation Measurement (pp. 343-353): Springer.
- Kling, H., Fuchs, M., & Paulin, M. (2012). *Runoff conditions in the upper Danube basin under an ensemble of climate change scenarios*. Journal of Hydrology, 424, 264-277.
- Lu, X., Tang, G., Liu, X., Wang, X., Liu, Y., & Wei, M. (2021). *The potential and uncertainty of triple collocation in assessing satellite precipitation products in Central Asia*. Atmospheric Research, 252, 105452.
- Nazeer, A., Maskey, S., Skaugen, T., & McClain, M. E. (2022). *Simulating the hydrological regime of the snow fed and glacialised Gilgit Basin in the Upper Indus using global precipitation products and a data parsimonious precipitation-runoff model*. Science of The Total Environment, 802, 149872.
- Parajka, J., Merz, R., & Blöschl, G. (2007). *Uncertainty and multiple objective calibration in regional water balance modelling: case study in 320 Austrian catchments*. Hydrological Processes: An International Journal, 21(4), 435-446.
- Qi, W., Yong, B., & Gourley, J. J. (2021). *Monitoring the Super Typhoon Lekima by GPM-based near-real-time satellite precipitation estimates*. Journal of Hydrology, 126968.

- Satgé, F., Defrance, D., Sultan, B., Bonnet, M.-P., Seyler, F., Rouché, N., . . . Paturel, J.-E. (2020). *Evaluation of 23 gridded precipitation datasets across West Africa*. *Journal of Hydrology*, 581, 124412.
- Sevruk, B. (1987). *Point precipitation measurements: why are they not corrected*. *Water for the future: Hydrology in perspective*, 447-457.
- Shi, H., Chen, J., Li, T., & Wang, G. (2017). *A new method for estimation of spatially distributed rainfall through merging satellite observations, raingauge records, and terrain digital elevation model data*. *Journal of Hydro-environment Research*.
- Sorman, A. A., Emin, T., & Dogan, Y. O. (2020). *Comparison of hydrological models in upper Aras basin*. *Pamukkale Üniversitesi Mühendislik Bilimleri Dergisi*, 26(6), 1015-1022.
- Sorooshian, S., Hsu, K.-L., Gao, X., Gupta, H. V., Imam, B., & Braithwaite, D. (2000). *Evaluation of PERSIANN system satellite-based estimates of tropical rainfall*. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 81(9), 2035-2046.
- Su, J., Li, X., Ren, W., Lü, H., & Zheng, D. (2021). *How reliable are the satellite-based precipitation estimations in guiding hydrological modelling in South China?* *Journal of Hydrology*, 602, 126705.
- Uysal, G., Hafizi, H., & Sorman, A. A. (2021). *Spatial and temporal evaluation of multiple gridded precipitation datasets over complex topography and variable climate of Turkey*. Paper presented at the EGU General Assembly Conference Abstracts.
- Uysal, G., & Şorman, A. Ü. (2021). *Evaluation of PERSIANN family remote sensing precipitation products for snowmelt runoff estimation in a mountainous basin*. *Hydrological Sciences Journal*, 1-18.
- Xie, P., Chen, M., Yang, S., Yatagai, A., Hayasaka, T., Fukushima, Y., & Liu, C. (2007). *A Gauge-Based Analysis of Daily Precipitation over East Asia*. *Journal of Hydrometeorology*, 8(3), 607-626.
- Zambrano-Bigiarini, M., Nauditt, A., Birkel, C., Verbist, K., & Ribbe, L. (2017). *Temporal and spatial evaluation of satellite-based rainfall estimates across the complex topographical and climatic gradients of Chile*. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 21(2), 1295.
- Zambrano-Bigiarini, M. a. B.-V., O. (2020). *Tutorial for using hydroPSO to calibrate TUWmodel*. doi:10.5281/zenodo.3772176